

CURE DEPENDENT CREEP COMPLIANCE OF AN EPOXY RESIN

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SUMMARY: The cure dependent creep compliance of a difunctional epoxide/tetrafunctional amine epoxy is investigated. Creep data at several cure states is taken over a range of temperatures and shifted according to time-temperature superposition to obtain master curves. The dependence of creep behavior on cure state is shown to be quite dramatic. Fully cured non-stoichiometric specimens are used to determine the equilibrium compliance of the partially cured material. The creep behavior of the partially cured material is shown to be significantly different from the non-stoichiometric material. This difference is attributed to free uncured amines that act as a diluent phase in the partially cured specimens.

KEYWORDS: curing, process modeling, creep, epoxy, viscoelasticity

INTRODUCTION

Modeling of residual stresses and warpage in composites is particularly difficult because the matrix constitutive behavior spans the entire range of liquid to solid during processing. Some recent research has been devoted to process modeling of residual stresses in curing polymer composites [1, 2]. Such models are extremely sensitive to the accuracy of constitutive models that describe the matrix viscoelastic behavior as a function of cure state. A detailed study of cure effects on stress relaxation of a Bisphenol A-derived epoxy cure state was recently reported in [3].

In this paper, the creep response of a Bisphenol F-derived epoxy is measured at several cure states and reported. A novel approach to obtain the full spectrum of creep response above T_g for partially cured specimens is also presented.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The resin that was used in this study is EPON Resin 862 (Shell Chemical, Houston, TX), a bifunctional epoxide formulated from the reaction of epichlorohydrin and Bisphenol F [4]. The epoxide was cured with EPON Curing Agent W (Shell Chemical, Houston, TX), diethyltoluene diamine. The chemical structure of both materials is shown in.

Figure 1: Resin system investigated for this study, EPON 862(bisphenol F epoxide) and EPON Curing Agent W (diethyltoluene diamine)

Four sets of specimens were manufactured using stoichiometric mixtures of epoxide and amine (26.4/100 epoxide/amine, by weight). The first set was cured for 10 hours at 177 °C while the second, third, and fourth sets were cured at 145 °C for 120, 50, and 40 minutes, respectively. The total heat of reaction of the uncured mixture was measured with a Polymer Labs differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) and determined to be 400 ± 11.2 J/g. The cure state of the four sets of specimens was determined by measuring the residual heat of reaction so that,

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{H_R}{H_T} \quad (1)$$

where α is the cure state, H_R is the residual heat and H_T is the total heat of reaction. For the cure cycles chosen, the cure states ranged from 0.68 to 1.0. The glass transition temperature, T_g , of these specimens was also measured using the DSC by scanning at a heating rate of 20 °C/min from room temperature to 180 °C. The T_g was fixed as the temperature corresponding to the midpoint of the heat capacity change at the glass transition. Figure 2 gives the cure state dependence of T_g for this material.

Figure 2: T_g dependence on cure state

Once cured, small beams (3mm x 2mm x 18mm) were cut from the bulk material. Creep tests were then performed in three-point bending over an appropriate temperature range to obtain the creep compliance master curve. Generally this range was from 30 °C to T_g . However, since the cure state of the fully cured material is not altered significantly by heating above T_g , data for these specimens was taken at temperatures up to 190 °C (~40 °C above T_g). The T_g is close to room temperature for $\alpha=0.68$, and so creep tests were begun at 5 °C for these specimens.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the creep tests are shown in Figure 3. The data at each cure state display time-temperature equivalence, and all data are shifted to a reference temperature of 30°C. The results indicate that small changes in the cure state have a profound effect on retardation especially at the lower degrees of cure. It is also worth noting that the initial compliance of the material is relatively insensitive to the cure state. This behavior was also observed by Kim and White [3] for another epoxy resin, Hercules 3501-6.

Figure 3: Creep compliance for a stoichiometric mixture of EPON 862/W at various cure states

Unfortunately, for partially cured materials the entire creep compliance curves up to the equilibrium compliance in the rubbery region cannot be measured. DSC experiments on partially cured specimens indicate that even short time (10 min) creep testing at temperatures above T_g will change the cure state of the material. For example, the measured T_g of an $\alpha=0.81$ specimen was 89.6°C before creep testing (10 min) at 93°C. After the creep test, the measured T_g had risen to 94.5 °C. As a result, no reliable data could be obtained at temperatures above T_g for the partially cured specimens.

An alternative approach is to adjust the stoichiometry of the epoxide-amine mixture to obtain “partially cured” specimens. In this technique, the amine concentration is decreased from the theoretical stoichiometric amount so that the heat of reaction is equal to $(H_T - H_R)$ of the partially cured stoichiometric specimens. Such samples can then be fully cured at high temperature, but will still contain unreacted epoxide groups.

To investigate the possibility of using this technique to obtain the complete master curves, three additional sets of specimens were manufactured from non-stoichiometric epoxide/amine mixtures corresponding to the cure states of the three sets of partially cured stoichiometric specimens. The epoxide/amine ratios for these specimens were 23.8/100, 21.4/100, and 18.0/100 to obtain cure states of 0.90, 0.81, and 0.68 respectively after curing for 10 hours at 177 °C.

The cure states of these specimens were checked by comparing the total heats of reaction of the non-stoichiometric and stoichiometric mixtures with the relation,

$$\alpha_{ns} = \frac{H_{ns}}{H_T} \quad (2)$$

where α_{ns} is the cure state of the non-stoichiometric specimens, H_T is the total heat of reaction of the stoichiometric mixture, and H_{ns} is the total heat of reaction of the non-stoichiometric mixture. The heat of reaction was found to be linearly dependent on weight fraction of amine as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Cure states for fully cured non-stoichiometric specimens

However as Figure 5 shows, DSC experiments of the non-stoichiometric specimens indicate that the T_g of the partially cured stoichiometric and the non-stoichiometric specimens are different. The T_g of a stoichiometric specimen is suppressed considerably compared to the

corresponding non-stoichiometric specimen. This effect could possibly be due to free primary amine molecules that have been trapped in the network, acting as a diluent phase. This suppression of T_g by the presence of a low molecular weight diluent has been shown to be significant for other polymers [5]. For example, less than five percent by weight of ethyl acetate in polystyrene reduces T_g by more than 15 °C. Nielsen [6] termed this behavior the *copolymer effect*, describing two possibly competing mechanisms in the evolution of T_g ; the degree of cross-linking which will always increase T_g , and the copolymer effect which can increase or decrease T_g depending on the nature of the curing agent. Another explanation for the difference in T_g could be the presence of unattached chains in the network of the partially cured stoichiometric specimens. An increase in relaxation behavior has been attributed even to long chains distributed throughout a cross-linked network [5].

Figure 5: Dependence of glass transition temperature on cure state

Figure 6 shows the dependence of the creep behavior on cure state for the non-stoichiometric specimens. Compared to the data for the stoichiometric specimens, there is a relatively small change in the creep behavior over the range of cure states studied. Indeed, the data for $\alpha_{ns}=0.90$ and fully cured stoichiometric specimens overlay with only a slight difference in the equilibrium compliance. However, the data still shows no significant change in the initial compliance with cure state.

Figure 6: Creep compliance for various non-stoichiometric epoxide/amine mixtures

Figure 7 shows the combined data for both the stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric specimens. The stoichiometric data indicate a strong dependence on cure state as the peak retardation time, estimated as the maximum slope in the creep master curve, spans approximately six decades. Figure 8 gives the temperature dependence of the shift factor for the two types of specimens. In all cases except $\alpha = 0.68$, there is a distinct bilinear character to the shift factor temperature dependence. The slopes of the curves above and below the transition are roughly the same. The discrepancy between the non-stoichiometric and stoichiometric data can be attributed to the suppression of T_g in the stoichiometric specimens as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 7: Creep compliance for partially cured stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric data

Figure 8: Temperature dependence of the shift factor for stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric specimens at various cure states

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, the cure dependent creep compliance of an epoxy resin was investigated. It was shown that for the resin system chosen, the peak retardation time varies by six decades of time (min) from cure states of $\alpha = 0.68$ to $\alpha = 1.0$. To obtain the entire master curve for the partially cured material, the possibility of using fully cured non-stoichiometric specimens in order to obtain creep data at higher temperature was investigated. However, the retardation behavior of the non-stoichiometric specimens is significantly different from their stoichiometric counterparts. This discrepancy is attributed to the suppression of T_g in the stoichiometric specimens due to uncured primary amines that act as a diluent phase.

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